

THERMOPLASTIC UD REINFORCED PROFILES: MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF LOCALLY FORMED PARTS

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SUMMARY

Based on a processing parameter's map for forming curved profiles with high fibre alignment in the formed section 90° angles were formed and mechanical characterised using three different load conditions. Effect of different forming parameters was studied regarding mechanical performance.

***Keywords:** profile forming, curvature shape, mechanical properties, UD reinforcements, thermoplastics.*

INTRODUCTION

The rise of interest in forming processes; i.e. manufacturing processes that transform a flat sheet or profile of composite into a three dimensional shape, for fibre reinforced composites is directly tied to the development of advanced thermoplastic composite materials. The forming of completely heated sheets or profiles has been investigated very intensively in the past [1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9]. During forming bending stresses are applied to the portions required to receive curvatures. A variety of defects take place at the inner curvature side of the formed parts such as in-plane fibre wrinkling and out-of-plane fibre buckling, these defects usually occur when there is not enough interply slip and the inner layers come under compression. Usually fibre buckling is accompanied by other failure modes such like fibre disorientation and initiated crack propagation. Recent study has been carried out to elaborate the effect of the processing parameters on the fibre alignment and orientations during forming on 90° v-shaped matched die bending samples [10]. A processing parameters' map was developed indicating the best parameter selections leading to defect-free parts with well aligned fibres. Heating length, heating time, setting temperature, and holding temperature time were the used processing parameters.

EXPERIMENTAL WORK

The work carried out here is focused on the mechanical performance of the formed parts. Two major topics are addressed. First the test configuration for characterisation of the mechanical behaviour of formed parts was studied, i.e. angle opening by tensile or three point bending load and angle closing by compression load. Second, the optimisation of processing conditions of forming process in terms of the mechanical properties was aimed. The processing map (Fig. 1) elaborated before [10] was used to avoid all the processing selections where different fibre failure modes were obtained. So, mainly formed parts with well oriented fibres were investigated (Table 1). Profile material used in the present study was a 24 mm × 4 mm (width × thickness) UD GF/PP profile manufactured by COMAT GmbH and commercially known as DExWin® [11], the profile fibre content is 60 wt.-% with a density of 1.55 g/cm³.

Fig. 1: Processing map indicating process parameter sets resulting in well aligned fibres in the formed region

Table 1: Selected forming processing parameters for mechanical performance optimization

Processing temp. [°C]	160.2		181.6				218.9			
Heating trace/ setting temp. [°C]	170	190	190	230	260	290	230	260	290	350
Heating time [min]	14:00	6:54	14:00	5:34	3:51	2:56	14:00	6:27	4:42	2:12
Holding time [min]	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	1		1				1			
	2		2				2			
Heating length [mm]	60	60	40	40	40	40	20	20	20	40
			60	60	60	60	40	40	40	60
							60	60	60	

Testing Methods

For testing the v-shaped parts three different testing set-ups as shown in (Fig. 2) were used.

Fig. 2: Testing configurations used for mechanical characterisation:
a) Angle opening by three point bending loading
b) Angle opening by tensile loading
c) Angle closing by compression loading

Great efforts have been made to overcome the lack of existing mechanical testing tool for testing under tensile and compression loading of curvature parts. As a result, a special fixture has been designed to allow defined loading of the samples.

Both tensile and compression tests were carried out using a universal testing machine (Zwick/Roell model 1474) with 10 kN load cell, 10 N preload, and 6 mm/min cross head velocity. Also, standard 3-point-bending fixture was used to perform bending tests. The tests were carried out under the previous testing machine and testing parameters, while the distance between lower supporting points was 45 mm.

For all test configurations the resulting force displacement curves were analysed and first failure was assumed for first point of force decrease. This first force maximum was used to compare samples manufactured using different processing parameters. The stiffness was analysed in the region between 0.05 mm and 0.20 mm displacement.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

It is very important to understand the mechanism of force and its behaviour during tension or compression at the curvature part (Fig. 3). In case of applying tension into a flat profile (two dimensional) the applied force is going to act axially with the unidirectional fibres, but in case of curvature profile (three dimensional) the applied force is going to act axially and perpendicularly which means that on-axis and off-axis stresses are obtained during tension or compression. The off-axis stress is mainly producing shear forces inside the lamina.

Fig. 3 Force analysis during tension and compression loading

In unidirectional composite, the fibre is the reinforcement in the axial direction while it has low ability to withstand with the non-axial stresses and the presence of the matrix is very helpful in this direction. In other words, the fibres are carrying axial loads and the matrix is carrying the transverse loads. Accordingly, the area of curvature; the area between points A-A` and B-B` are going to expose excessive interlaminar shear stresses during tensile and compression respectively, this is explaining why crack propagating and lamina delaminating always takes place at the shear area.

Effect of Processing Parameters on Tensile Properties

Fig. 4: Relationship between processing parameters and tensile force for curvature with highly oriented fibres (white background)

The relation between different processing parameters and maximum tensile force is exemplarily shown in Fig. 4. The processing parameters that produce curvatures with highly oriented fibres at both inner and outer sides are highlighted with white background. An increase in tensile force with increasing heating length is found for nearly all processing parameter combinations.

As discussed and concluded in previous work [10], increasing heating length leads to a decrease in thickness and an increase in fibre contents at the curvature area. In tensile configuration the angle opening load results in tensile forces especially at the inner curvature and the well aligned fibres are capable to bear the major part of the load. As known, the ability of UD lamina to withstand with axial stresses increase with fibre content while it is relatively decreasing with non-axial stresses. The result shows that tensile strength is increased with heating length as fibre content increased as a result of squeezing matrix and decreasing thickness. This action is expanding by increasing processing temperatures till reaching a level that decreasing matrix content become very critical to withstand with off-axis stress, this explains the decrease in tensile strength at maximum processing temperature and heating length.

Fig. 5: Relationship between processing parameters and tensile stiffness for curvature with highly oriented fibres (white background)

As a conclusion from Fig. 4 it is very remarkable that highest tensile strength could be achieved only in two categories; maximum processing temperature (218.9 °C) with medium heating length (40 mm), and medium processing temperature (181.6 °C) with maximum heating length (60 mm).

The relation between different processing parameters and the tensile stiffness is presented in Fig. 5. For low processing temperatures an only minor effect of processing temperatures is found. Increasing the processing temperature results in more pronounced matrix squeeze during forming and this affects the stiffness more pronounced since the global specimen stiffness is calculated which does not cover the local decrease in thickness in the curvature.

Effect of Processing Parameters on Compressive Properties

Compression testing results in an angle closing loading of the samples and here the well alignment of the fibres at the inner curvature does not support the loading. In contrast to tensile loading here the maximum compression force is slightly decreasing with increasing heating length, for low processing temperatures (Fig. 6), or mostly unaffected, for high processing temperature. The compressive stiffness behaves fully analogue to the force, i.e. slightly decreasing at lower processing temperature and mostly unaffected for high processing temperature.

Fig. 6: Relationship between processing parameters and compressive force for curvature with highly oriented fibres (white background)

Fig. 6 already indicates, higher compressive forces are beared by profiles having fibre buckling in the curvature. This effect is much more pronounced if curvatures are processed at a low temperature level (PT: 160.2°C) in combination with low heating length (Fig. 7). Here the fibre buckling is located in the curvature region (Fig. 8) and it seems the buckled fibres are acting as a supporting, load bearing element.

Effect of Processing Parameters on Flexure Properties

In three point bending configuration the angle is loaded in opening direction again. The effect of processing parameters is fully in line with the tensile loading configuration (Fig. 9).

Fig. 7: Relationship between processing parameters and compressive force for curvature processed at low temperature

Fig. 8: μ CT-scan of curvature exhibiting fibre buckling

Fig. 9: Relationship between processing parameters and three point bending force for curvature with highly oriented fibres (white background)

Fig. 10: Processing map for receiving highest load bearing capability under angle opening load configuration (three point bending indicated as flexural)

Optimizing processing parameters

Establishing a forming processing map for high mechanical properties is the major theme of this work. It is necessary first to determine the data range which should enter into the map and represent the highest measured values of the property. All readings located on the upper quartile of the test series were selected for optimisation purpose, i.e. maximum tensile force above 200 N and maximum three point bending force above 500 N. Depending on the heating length used, different sets of processing parameters are needed to receive highest load bearing capability (Fig. 10).

The choice of optimised processing parameters depends on the final application of the curved parts, depending on whether angle opening or angle closing loading is applied in service, the processing of curvature has to be performed in different ways.

CONCLUSION

Based on the results elaborated the processing map defined before was extended to identify the processing window resulting in formed parts exhibiting best fibre orientation, no defects, and highest mechanical performance.

The load configuration results in different effects depending on whether the formed angle is opened or closed under load. But, under similar load configurations the kind of sample fixation during testing does hardly affect the dependency between processing parameter set and resulting mechanical behaviour. In detail, the results showed that increasing heating length and processing temperature individually or in combination leads in most cases to an increase in tensile strength and a decrease in tensile modulus. The same conclusion is made for three point bending. For compressive strength and stiffness it has been shown, well aligned fibres in the curved region are not the best way to receive highest load bearing capability.

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